

ATTITUDES OF PARENTS TO CHILDREN'S PARTICIPATION IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION CLASSES

Hüseyin Öztürk^{1*}, Ahmet Yılmaz²,
Gamze Peksayılır¹, Zeynep Yılmaz Öztürk³

¹Gaziantep University, Physical Education and
Sport Science Department, Gaziantep, Turkey

²Kilis 7 December University, Kilis, Turkey

³Gaziantep Sahinbey Science and Art Center,
Gaziantep, Turkey

Abstract:

This study was prepared with the aim of determining the attitudes of the parents about students who study the formal secondary schools affiliated the Ministry of Education of Adiyaman province to physical education lessons. Target population of the research is 435 parents whose children attending secondary education institutions affiliated to the central district of Adiyaman in the academic year 2016-2017. The attitude scale consisting of 21 items was used in the research. Attitude scale consists of 4 sub-dimensions. These dimensions are; perceptive, functional, supportive and important. As a result; it is seen that there is a meaningful difference between the attitudes of the parents towards the physical education lesson according to the sporting situations and educational status of the parents.

Keywords: physical education, family, attitude

1. Introduction

Attitude was firstly discussed in the 19th century as a scientific matter. This concept, which is originally Latin, is described as ready for action (Arkonaç, 2001). It's also defined the approach of accepting or disapproving a situation that is welcomed by individuals (Başaran, 1991).

¹ Correspondence: email hozturk@gantep.edu.tr

Attitude can be characterized as a continuous organization of the motivation, enthusiasm, learning and perception processes of the perception worlds of their own (Krech et al., 1980). Attitude does not have the readiness to show any treatment against such things, with close or distance to some objects, positions and notions (Hilgard et al., 1971). Attitude is not a directly measurable concept, but it is possible to indirectly measure it through the behavior of a person (Kagıtcıbası, 2005).

Physical education is all of the regular work carried out with the aim of providing physical, spiritual and intellectual development of the people, strengthening the national consciousness and citizenship feelings and preparing the individuals for the daily life, the conditions of the business world (Yalcın, 1995). It can also be defined as the training of the individual with physical exercises (Tamer and Pular, 2001). Physical education is all sportive activities based on interchangeable rules that vary according to the characteristics of the individual and the circumstances, when necessary, in order to improve physical and mental health and physical skills of the individuals (Aracı, 2004; Alıncak et al, 2016, Alıncak, 2016).

Sport is a cultural phenomenon that includes both competition and solidarity and socialization, body and soul development, in leisure time or in an all-inclusive manner, with or without tools in various frameworks in the process of developing the talents that the individual acquires while naturalizing the natural environment of the individual (Goral ve Yapıcı, 2001). In physical education and sports activities, the students have learned to learn various ways of interacting, protecting their physical health and being a shareholder, acting in cooperation, accepting success, accepting defeat and developing a strategy towards a target (Seckin ve Basbay, 2013).

There are also a number of features that the physical education course can develop on its own. These characteristics in general terms; to improve the physical capacity of the individual and to learn to be sensitive to rules (Mulayim, 2014). Being able to understanding of people's physical education and sports world begins with the family. Participation in the physical education and sporting activities of the child and the extent of participation is affected by the attitude of parents to socialization (Larson, 1970).

The aim of this study is to examine the attitudes of the parents of the secondary students in the developing provinces (Example of Adiyaman province) towards Physical Education and Sports lessons but also it is important because quite a few number of research done in this field on this sample.

2. Method

In this section, the research model, target population of the research, the data collection tools to be used in the research will be mentioned.

2.1 Research Model

In this study, it was aimed to measure the attitudes of the parents of the students who attended the public secondary schools affiliated to the Ministry of National Education in Adiyaman province. Descriptive method was used in the research. The descriptive method is described as a situation determination aiming to reveal any existing situation (Buyukozturk, 2005).

2.2 Population and Sample

The target population of the research is composed of the parents of the students attending the secondary schools of the Ministry of Education in Adiyaman. When sampling is chosen, random sampling method is used. The random sampling method is a sampling method in which each individual in the study universe has an equal chance of being selected (Arli and Nazik, 2004). With random sampling, 435 parents have been included in the sampling. Personal data belonging to the parents included in this research are presented in Table 1.

2.3 Research Group

The sample group of the research sample is the parents of 9th, 10th and 11th grades students who study the formal secondary schools affiliated the Ministry of Education of Adiyaman province in the academic year 2016-2017.

2.4 Data Collection Tools

As a means of data collection in research; "attitude scale of parents' attitude to children's participation in physical education lessons" which is developed by Oncu (2007) was used. In the first part of the scale, there are 7 questions about the demographic characteristics of the individuals. The scale is in Likert type with a score of 1-5. Factor analysis was performed to test the validity of the scale. For the reliability study, internal consistency coefficient (Cronbach Alpha) value was calculated and calculated as 0.69. A total of 750 scales were distributed to the schools where the research was carried out and 435 were eliminated. The turnover rate of the district is 58%.

Before the scale was distributed, the students were told about the purpose and importance of researching them on behalf of their parents.

3. Results

Table 1: Personal information pertaining to the attitudes of the parents' attitude to children's participation in physical education lessons

Groups	N	F	%
Gender	Female	276	63.4
	Male	159	36.6
Sporting activities	Yes	93	21.4
	No	342	78.6
Educational status	Primary School	177	40.7
	Secondary School	133	30.6
	High School	85	19.5
	University and higher	40	9.2
Age	26-33	51	11.7
	34-41	159	36.6
	42 years and over	225	51.7
Income Status	1300-1600 TL	243	55.9
	1601-2500 TL	115	26.4
	2501-3000TL	44	10.1
	3001 TL. And over	33	7.6
Watching sporting programs on TV	Most of the time	85	19.5
	Sometimes	199	45.7
	No	151	34.7

Table 1 shows the distribution of the answers given to questions about personal characteristics of the research group. According to this; 63.4% (276 persons) of the participants were women. It was found that 78.6% of the participants (342 people) do not any kind of sports; 40.7% (177 people) were primary school graduates; 51.7% (225 people) were 42 years old and over; 55.9% (243 people) had a low level of 1300-1600 liras and 45.7% of them watched sports programs on TV sometimes.

Table 2: Distribution of attitude scores towards physical education classes according to gender of parents

Factor	Gender	N	Avg.	Ss	t	p
Perceptive	Female	276	4.54	0.60	0.78	0.47
	Male	159	4.58	0.51		
Functional	Female	276	2.65	0.89	2.40	0.17
	Male	159	2.46	0.69		
Supportive	Female	276	3.59	0.82	1.06	0.28
	Male	159	3.49	1.04		
Importance	Female	276	2.59	0.94	0.28	0.78
	Male	159	2.62	0.87		
Total	Female	276	3.54	0.40	1.06	0.28
	Male	159	3.49	0.46		

p<0.05

When Table 2 was examined, there was no significant difference between the attitude scale and subscale of the parents who participated in the study according to the sex, the attitude towards the participation in Physical Education course of their children. Results as forward: (Perceptive; $t=0.78$, $p>0.05$), (Functional; $t=2.40$, $p>0.05$), (Support; $t=1.06$, $p>0.05$), (Importance; $t=0.28$, $p>0.05$), (Total; $t=1.06$, $p>0.05$).

Table 3: Distribution of attitude scores towards physical education classes according to sportive activities of parents

Factor	Sporting activities	N	Avg.	Ss	t	p
Perceptive	Yes	93	4.56	0.56	0.37	0.97
	No	342	4.56	0.57		
Functional	Yes	93	2.36	0.84	2.88	0.04*
	No	342	2.64	0.82		
Support	Yes	93	3.23	0.82	3.78	0.00*
	No	342	3.63	0.91		
Importance	Yes	93	2.29	0.89	3.72	0.00*
	No	342	2.62	0.91		
Total	Yes	93	3.35	0.36	4.39	0.00*
	No	342	3.57	0.43		

$p<0.05$

When Table 3 is examined, there is no statistically significant difference between the scores of parents' attitude scores towards physical education lessons according to sporting activities variable with subscale of perceptive ($t=0.37$, $p>0.05$), but on the other hand there is a statistically significant difference between subscale of functional ($t=2.88$, $p<0.05$), subscale of support ($t=3.78$, $p<0.05$), subscale of importance ($t=3.72$, $p<0.05$), and the total score ($t=4.39$, $p<0.05$).

Table 4: ANOVA Test Resultsof Attitude Scores towards Physical Education Classes according to Educational Status of Parents

Factor	Educational Status	N	Avg.	SS	F	p	Significant Difference
Perceptive	Primary School (a)	177	4.37	0.64	16.6	0.00*	(a<b,c,d),(b<d)
	Secondary School (b)	133	4.58	0.53			
	High School (c)	85	4.77	0.37			
	University and higher (d)	40	4.88	0.29			
Functional	Primary School (a)	177	2.77	0.85	13.4	0.00*	(a>b,c),(b>c,d)
	Secondary School (b)	133	2.67	0.71			
	High School (c)	85	2.29	0.73			
	University and higher (d)	40	2.05	0.88			
Supportive	Primary School (a)	177	3.89	0.75	19.5	0.00*	(a>b,c,d), (b>d)
	Secondary School (b)	133	3.45	0.87			
	High School (c)	85	3.25	1.03			
	University and higher (d)	40	3.29	0.65			
Importance	Primary School (a)	177	2.85	0.93	23.7	0.00*	(a>c,d), (b>c,d)
	Secondary School (b)	133	2.76	0.79			
	High School (c)	85	2.18	0.80			

	University and higher (d)	40	1.85	0.74			
Total	Primary School (a)	177	3.61	0.44			
	Secondary School (b)	133	3.56	0.38	10.7	0.00*	(a>c,d), (b>c,d)
	High School (c)	85	3.40	0.45			
	University and higher (d)	40	3.27	0.51			

p<0.05

When Table 4 is examined, perceptive subscale scores showed that parents who graduated from secondary school, high school, university and higher were significantly higher than those who were graduated from primary school and those who graduated from university or higher were significantly higher than those who were graduated from high schools. Functional subscale scores were found to be significantly higher for the parents who graduated from primary school than those who graduated from secondary school and those who graduated from high schools were significantly higher than those who were graduated from university or higher. Support subscale scores showed that the parents who graduated from primary school had higher scores than secondary and high school graduates and those who graduated from secondary and high schools were significantly higher than those who were graduated from university or higher. Significant subscale scores showed that the parents who graduated from primary school had higher scores than the parents who graduated from high school, university or higher and parents who graduated from secondary school had higher scores than the parents who graduated university or higher. According to the total scale, the parents who graduated from primary school were found to have significantly higher scores than the parents who graduated from high school, university or higher.

According to this result, as education level increases, attitudes towards physical education lesson decrease. It can be considered that the biggest factor affecting this outcome is the exam anxiety.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

In our study, the attitudes of the parents of the secondary education students of different income levels towards Physical Education and Sports lesson in Adıyaman province were examined according to some variables. There was no statistically significant difference between the findings of the study according to gender variable.

There are studies with similar results in the literature. Cohen's (2005) study found that there were no significant differences between parental attitudes by parents' gender. As a result of the studies conducted by Öncü (2007) and Yaldız (2013), it is concluded that there is no meaningful difference regarding the attitudes of the parents to the Physical Education lessons according to their genders. Öztürk and his colleagues

(2016) found no statistically significant difference between the sexes of the parents who sent their children to basketball schools. The research group Öztürk and Abakay (2014) did not find a significant difference in parents' attitudes towards children with disabilities according to age and sex.

There are also studies that have different results in the literature. These; The results of the research carried out by Stelzer et al. (2004), Hünük (2006) and Koca and Demirhan (2004) concluded that there was a significant difference between the attitudes of parents to the Physical Education lessons by the male and female paediatricians. When we look at the attitudes of the Veli to the physical education lesson according to the sporting situation, it is seen that the sportsmen have more positive attitude towards the Physical Education lesson.

Studies that have similar results in the literature; it has been determined that the parents who play sports have a more positive attitude towards the physical education lesson than those who do not play sports in the studies of Öncü (2007) and Yaldız (2013).

Harris (1999) and Cohen (2005) found that the attitudes of the parents to the physical education lesson; as a result of differences in sport situations. Öztürk and Abakay (2014) made a significant difference according to whether or not the parents who participated in the research had previously played sports. Kangalgil and his colleagues (2004), Güllü and Güçlü (2009) are supportive of this research with their previous work on the sporting parents.

In the study of Kanters et al. (2007), the fact that the parents had previously engaged in sports made it possible for the child and the family to agree on the sports. When we examine the attitudes of the parents towards the participation of the children in the physical education lesson according to their educational status, it is seen that there is also a meaningful difference. This result shows that Yaldız (2013) is similar to the result of his study, whereas Öncü (2007) does not.

5. Suggestions

It should be mentioned that in addition to academic achievement, the importance of sporting success and the impact of sporting achievement on academic achievement, necessary informational work should be undertaken at this point.

The welfare should be encouraged to perform sporting activities with various activities carried out and it should be mentioned that the parents of the children will give positive contributions to the development of their children.

School administrators and other branch teachers should be an example at this point with the importance and positive attitudes towards Physical Education.

It should be possible to organize sports competitions and races in the school and invite them as spectators, so that the success of their children will contribute to the development of positive thoughts towards the spore by the parents.

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